

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PRECONDITIONS FOR TEACHING SWIMMING TO PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract

Swimming as a type of physical exercise is an almost ideal model for studying the problems of the theory of learning motor actions, as here we are dealing with the complete absence of any skill, such as the habit of moving in the water. According to some data, the formation of swimming skills depends on the level of development of motor skills. Children with a high level of motor skills control are more likely to outperform others in learning to swim. And in order to raise a child's genetic abilities, we need to know what those abilities are and how to develop them. The specificity of the aquatic environment leaves a significant imprint on the learning process, which may explain the large number of options in swimming learning schemes. A number of authors propose to use the form of the training game when teaching swimming. However, despite the huge amount of methodological means and techniques used in teaching swimming, the possibilities of education for development, goal setting, propulsion systems, self-monitoring and self-assessment, i.e. what reflects the current state of teaching, are not yet sufficiently used.

Keywords: swimming, children, psychological precondition, pedagogical preconditions, means, training

In swimming, due to the specifics of the aquatic environment, the formation of motor skills has its own characteristics [9]. In water, the accuracy of movements is violated. Due to the fact that the organs of vision and hearing do not adapt well to activities in the aquatic environment, a person sees and hears worse in it, hardly determines the direction of movement, V.S. Farfel [4] indicates that the control of movements in the water is associated with the suppression of many ground motor automatisms, therefore, children with a high level of development of the ability to control movements had time to learn to swim. V.S. Farfel [4]; B.V. Rîşneac [15], A. A. Guzhalovsky [6] attached special importance to the ability of a swimmer to control the temporal, spatial and power characteristics of movements. In addition, in the works of T.S. Timakova [17] it was noted that qualified swimmers are distinguished by a high sensitivity of the skin analyzer, which plays a leading role in developing the perception of the “feeling of water”.

It is known that the formation of motility elements occurs unevenly and heterochronously. One of the ways to improve the efficiency of the technical training of swimmers is the use of training exercises, taking into account the sensitive periods of the age dynamics of individual indicators of swimming technique [1, 10]. Opportunities to control motor actions can be manifested in a conscious change in various parameters of technology, the magnitude of the developed efforts, the pace of swimming, the amplitude of preparatory

and working movements, the speed of movement, in constant control over the quality of movements.

Improving the regulatory functions of psychomotor is an additional way to implement the hidden reserves of athletes. If in the course of the educational process the necessary psychomotor qualities are specially and purposefully developed, it is possible to obtain an additional effect of the growth of technical skill, and by improving the regulatory functions of psychomotor, to find hidden reserves, improve the quality of motor action, reduce the training time. Many aspects of the problem of psychomotor development of young athletes are still far from the final solution, and this should become an incentive for their further in-depth development, in particular, the study of the problem of new approaches to the development of psychological and pedagogical aspects of teaching junior schoolchildren to swim.

To determine the level of development of children's abilities in the process of learning to swim, it is necessary to take into account the age at which training begins. Methodological recommendations for teaching preschool children are most detailed in the studies of a number of authors [2, 13, 14, 18 and others]. The younger school age is regarded by many authors as the most favorable for learning to swim. The most successful development of the skill takes place in the age range of 8-10 years. A.A. Kislov [8] considers the age of 7-8 years to be optimal for learning. The need for learning to swim at school age is evidenced by the data obtained by L.V. Stroeveva [16]: at the age of 7-8 years, 68-80% of schoolchildren cannot swim, at 9-10 years, 46-48% of schoolchildren. It should be noted that in many foreign countries swimming is taught to children of primary school age. This is facilitated by the psychological characteristics of this period of life. The age of the beginning of swimming lessons for boys and girls is somewhat different. These differences are due to a complex of reasons: more effective assimilation of swimming techniques by girls and other reasons associated with the advanced natural development of the female body. A favorable age for starting sprinters (crawl) can be considered 9-11 years old for boys and 8-10 years old for girls, stayers - 7-9 years old - (for boys and girls) and the same for girls specializing in breaststroke, butterfly, swimming on the back and complex swimming (this age for boys is 8-10 years old).

The study of age-specific features of the development of mental abilities of school-age persons allowed A.I. Pogrebnoy [12] to identify a number of patterns that determine the effectiveness of the educational process in swimming. At primary school age, the formation of a motor skill has gender characteristics. For boys 7-10 years old, the criteria for learning to swim are indicators that characterize the ability to control movements in terms of time, space and power parameters, using the features of motor memory, the mobility of the nervous system; for girls - the ability to control movements according to the main parameters; features of motor memory, representations, control of the tempo of a simple movement. Children with an increased level of learning are distinguished by a significant level of development of the ability to control movements and mental functions.

Many researchers [4, 12, 15 and others] indicate the relationship between the ability to control certain parameters movements with success in learning to swim.

The learning process can be shortened by deliberately organizing the orientation activities of the children being taught. The organization of feedback gives a particularly great effect. The further way of optimizing the learning process will inevitably require, in addition to general methodological rationalization, the introduction of individual programs of pedagogical influences into the educational process, that is, the construction of a system of directed activity style.

So, T.S. Timakova [17] notes that for 9-10 years old girls, along with a large contribution of mental abilities, their progress in swimming is influenced by their motor preparedness. In boys, the contribution of mental processes increases without reducing the factors of motor fitness. N.V.Ermolova [3] points to the fact that in boys during the initial swimming training, some mental abilities are manifested to a lesser extent than in girls.

In the studies of I.G. Karaseva [7] it was shown that for swimmers, the properties of the nervous system associated with its lability, mobility and endurance are professionally significant. The importance of general mental (intellectual) abilities in swimming has been proven.

When learning to swim, the student is faced with many distractions associated with changing the vertical position to a horizontal one, with changes in the temperature of the water and air environment. All these factors lead to a dispersion of the child's attention, and a decrease in the amount of memorized educational information. Therefore, when teaching swimming, it is necessary to constantly concentrate the attention of the child, and develop his memory.

G.D. Gorbunov [5] comes to the conclusion that mental adaptation to swimming loads is carried out slowly, and therefore has a positive effect on the concentration of attention, but can negatively affect memory, especially its volume. Unaccustomed loads have a negative effect on memory, a positive effect on operational thinking and information retrieval, reaction time and attention remain unchanged. The stability of mental processes is directly dependent on the level of physical fitness.

During the after-effect of swimming loads, the nature of the course of mental processes (in the direction of improvement or deterioration) depends on the nature of the load, adaptation to them, the level of structure of mental processes, and so on. Mnemonic functions are the most "sensitive" to physical loads. It is noted that high results are achieved by swimmers with high personal, volitional qualities, sensory-perceptual culture.

The participation of various mental qualities in achieving a high level of swimming training for boys and girls is not the same. Boys who successfully learn to swim differ from those who lag behind in learning in terms of the quality of memorization, specialized motor representations, the volume of motor memory, the time of mental training and the ability to control the temporal parameters of movements. Successfully trained girls differ in the quality of specialized motor representations, the volume of motor memory and the ability to control the temporal parameters of movements from the girls lagging behind in learning to swim.

According to experts [1, 11, 16], the effectiveness of initial training is significantly increased if the accents of training influences coincide in nature with natural development of mental and physical qualities.

Thus, having analyzed the psychological and pedagogical features of teaching swimming to children of primary school age, it should be noted that learning ability is a complex property determined by genetically determined mental characteristics, morphological and functional indicators and physical fitness of the child. It is essential that in the process of teaching swimming it is possible to develop the motor and mental abilities of children, which in turn improves the quality of training, enriching it. However, when implementing didactic tasks in the process of teaching swimming, the psychomotor and cognitive abilities of children are still not sufficiently taken into account, as well as a number of other psychological factors associated with being in the aquatic environment.

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